

Kinetic study for the oxidation of *dl*-mandelic acid by tripropylammonium fluorochromate in the absence and presence of picolinic acid and 1,10-phenanthroline

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Abstract : The oxidation of *dl*-mandelic acid (MA) by tripropylammonium fluorochromate (TriPAFC) has been studied in aqueous acetic acid medium. The oxidation leads to the formation of the phenyl glyoxalic acid. The reaction is first order with respect to TriPAFC, MA and [H⁺] and the reaction is catalyzed by hydrogen ions. The reaction has been studied in the presence of picolinic acid (PA) and 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen) as promoters. The promoters used in this oxidation reaction, picolinic acid (PA) and 1,10-phenanthroline (Phen) are strong chelating ligands which form complexes with most transition metal ions. Among the two promoters oxidation is much faster with 1,10-phenanthroline. The low dielectric constant of the medium assists the complex formation and enhances the reactivity. Various thermodynamic parameters have been determined at different acetic acid-water composition. A suitable mechanism has been proposed.

Keywords : Tripropylammonium fluorochromate, *dl*-mandelic acid, picolinic acid, 1,10-phenanthroline.

Introduction

Oxidation is a key reaction for different organic synthesis. The development of oxidizing agents based upon higher-valent transition metal oxo derivatives has been a subject of research in many laboratories, and a host of such reagents derived from ruthenium, osmium, iron, manganese, molybdenum, vanadium and chromium have all proven to be capable of alcohol oxidation. In particular, there is continued interest in the development of new Cr^{VI} reagents for the effective and selective oxidation of organic substrates, in particular alcohols, under mild conditions. Chromic acid is a widely used oxidizing agent. In recent years, significant improvements were achieved by the use of new oxidizing agents, such as tetrahexylammonium bromochromate¹, 4-benzylpyridinium fluorochromate², tetramethylammonium fluorochromate³, tributylammonium chlorochromate⁴, imidazolium fluorochromate⁵, tetraethyl ammonium bromochromate⁶, benzimidazolium fluorochromate⁷ and triethylammonium chlorochromate⁸.

Tripropylammonium fluorochromate is also one such

oxidant developed recently^{9,10}. It is a more efficient and stronger oxidizing agent. This new compound is more efficient for quantitative oxidation of several organic substrates and has certain advantages over similar oxidizing agents in terms of the amount of oxidant and solvent required, short reaction times and high yields.

Among the different chelating agents¹¹⁻¹⁶ that promote Cr^{VI} oxidation of different types of organic substrate, picolinic acid and 1,10-phenanthroline are quite important¹⁷⁻²³.

The kinetics and mechanism of oxidation of hydroxy acids by various oxidants have been reported²⁴⁻³². However, no detailed kinetic study of oxidation of *dl*-mandelic acid by TriPAFC in the absence and presence of promoters such as picolinic acid and 1,10-phenanthroline have so far been attempted. This prompted us to undertake the present investigation. Here we studied the kinetics of oxidation of *dl*-mandelic acid by TriPAFC in the absence and presence of picolinic acid and 1,10-phenanthroline, and observed that 1,10-phenanthroline is the most suitable promoter of this oxidation. Mechanistic aspects are also discussed.

Results and discussion

The oxidation of *dl*-mandelic acid by TriPAFC has been conducted in 50% acetic acid and 50% water medium at 303 K, under pseudo-first order conditions in the absence and presence of picolinic acid and 1,10-phenanthroline and the result obtained were discussed in the following paragraphs.

Effect of varying TriPAFC concentration : The concentration of TriPAFC was varied in the range of 0.6×10^{-3} to 3.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻³ at constant [MA], [H⁺] at 303 K and the rates were measured (Table 1). The near constancy in the value of k_{obs} irrespective of the concentration confirms the first order dependence on TriPAFC.

Effect of varying mandelic acid concentration : The concentration of MA is varied in the range of 1.0×10^{-2} to 3.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻³ at 303 K and keeping all other reactant concentrations as constant and the rates were measured (Table 1). The rate of oxidation increased progressively on increasing the concentration of mandelic acid. The plot of log k_{obs} versus log [MA] gave the slope of 1.03 for MA respectively (Fig. 1). Under pseudo-first order conditions, the plot of k_{obs} versus [MA] is linear passing through origin. These results confirm the first order nature of the reaction with respect to [MA].

Effect of varying perchloric acid concentration : Perchloric acid has been used as a source of H⁺ in reaction medium. The concentration of H⁺ was varied in the range 0.12 to 0.36 mol dm⁻³ keeping all other reactant concentration as constant at 303 K and the rates were measured (Table 1). The acid catalysed nature of this oxidation is confirmed by an increase in the rate on the addition of H⁺. The plot of log k_{obs} versus log [H⁺] is a straight line with the slope of 1.09. Therefore, order with respect to H⁺ is one for MA. TriPAFC may become protonated in the presence of acid and the protonated TriPAFC may function as an effective oxidant.

Effect of acrylonitrile and MnSO₄ : The reaction did not promote polymerization of acrylonitrile indicating the

absence of free radicals (Table 1). However, the addition of Mn^{II} (0.003 mol dm⁻³), in the form of MnSO₄ retards the rate of oxidation. This indicates the involvement of Cr^{IV} intermediate in the oxidation of hydroxy acids by Cr^{VI} reagent and confirms the two electron transfer process in the reaction. Mn^{II} ion reduces Cr^{IV} formed to Cr^{III}. In the absence of Mn^{II} ion, formed Cr^{IV} reduces Cr^{VI} to Cr^V and the oxidation of hydroxy acids by Cr^V is fast²⁰. The decrease in the rate of Cr^{VI} reduction on the addition of Mn^{II} has been attributed to the removal of Cr^{IV} by reaction with Mn^{II}.

Table 1. Rate constants for the oxidation of mandelic acid by TriPAFC in aqueous acetic acid medium at 303 K^a

10^3 [TriPAFC] (mol dm ⁻³)	10^2 [MA] (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^5 k_1^b$ (s ⁻¹)	$10^3 k_2^c$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)
0.6	2.0	0.24	41.10	20.55
1.2	2.0	0.24	41.18	20.59
1.8	2.0	0.24	41.26	20.63
2.4	2.0	0.24	41.30	20.65
3.0	2.0	0.24	41.20	20.60
1.2	1.0	0.24	20.92	20.92
1.2	1.5	0.24	31.64	20.43
1.2	2.5	0.24	51.30	20.52
1.2	3.0	0.24	62.00	20.67
1.2	2.0	0.12	20.66	1.72
1.2	2.0	0.18	30.76	1.71
1.2	2.0	0.30	51.42	1.71
1.2	2.0	0.36	61.80	1.72
1.2	2.0	0.24	41.24	20.62 ^d
1.2	2.0	0.24	35.28	17.64 ^e

^aAs determined by a spectrophotometric technique following the disappearance of oxidant.

10^2 [MA] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³; 10^3 [TriPAFC] = 1.2 mol dm⁻³; [H⁺] = 0.24 mol dm⁻³.

Solvent composition : 50% acetic acid-50% water (v/v).

^bEstimated from pseudo-first order plots over 80% reaction.

^cIndividual k_2 values estimated as $k_1/[MA]$ or $k_1/[H^+]$.

^dContained 0.001 mol dm⁻³ acrylonitrile.

^eIn the presence of 0.003 mol dm⁻³ Mn^{II}.

Effect of acidity : The reaction is catalyzed by hydrogen ions (Table 1). The acid-catalysis may well be attributed to a protonation of TriPAFC to give a stronger oxidant and electrophile.

The formation of a protonated Cr^{VI} species has earlier been postulated in the reactions of structurally similar PCC³³ and PFC³⁴.

Kinetic isotope effect :

To ascertain the importance of the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step, oxidation of α -deuterio mandelic acid (DMA) was studied. Results showed the presence of a substantial primary kinetic isotope effect (Table 2).

Table 2. Kinetic isotope effect on the oxidation of mandelic acid by TriPAFC

Substrate	$10^5 \times k_1$ (s ⁻¹)			
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K
MA	32.16	41.18	57.24	78.88
DMA	6.05	7.43	9.96	13.32
$k_{\text{H}}/k_{\text{D}}$	5.34	5.54	5.75	5.92

Solvent composition = 50% AcOH-50% H₂O (v/v)

10^2 [MA] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³; 10^3 [TriPAFC] = 1.2 mol dm⁻³; 10 [H⁺] = 2.4 mol dm⁻³.

Effect of varying picolinic acid and 1,10-phenanthroline concentration :

The concentration of picolinic acid and 1,10-phenanthroline were varied in the range of 0.0×10^{-3} to 10.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻¹ at constant [TriPAFC], [MA] and [H⁺] at 303 K and the rates were measured (Table 3). We observed that the rate increases linearly with increasing promoter concentration. For 1,10-phenanthroline the rate is much faster than picolinic acid, because of easy decomposition of the ternary complex of the active oxidant in the presence of 1,10-phenanthroline and mandelic acid, because of steric crowding.

Effect of varying TriPAFC and mandelic acid concentration in the presence of picolinic acid or 1,10-phenanthroline :

The values of k_{obs} were calculated in the presence of 6.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻¹ picolinic acid or 1,10-phenanthroline for different concentrations of TriPAFC by maintaining other parameters at constant values. The data in Table 3 show that the rate constant did not get much altered with

Table 3. Rate constants for the oxidation of mandelic acid by TriPAFC in aqueous acetic acid medium in the presence of picolinic acid or 1,10-phenanthroline at 303 K^a

10^3 [TriPAFC] (mol dm ⁻³)	10^2 [MA] (mol dm ⁻³)	[H ⁺] (mol dm ⁻³)	10^3 [Cat] (mol dm ⁻³)	$10^5 k_1^b$ (s ⁻¹)	
				PA	Phen
1.2	2.0	0.24	0.0	41.18	41.18
1.2	2.0	0.24	2.0	47.64	60.04
1.2	2.0	0.24	4.0	53.88	78.76
1.2	2.0	0.24	6.0	60.08	97.90
1.2	2.0	0.24	8.0	66.38	116.44
1.2	2.0	0.24	10.0	72.64	135.22
0.6	2.0	0.24	6.0	60.16	97.78
1.8	2.0	0.24	6.0	60.22	97.92
2.4	2.0	0.24	6.0	60.18	97.86
3.0	2.0	0.24	6.0	60.04	97.82
1.2	1.0	0.24	6.0	29.88	48.78
1.2	1.5	0.24	6.0	45.22	73.12
1.2	2.5	0.24	6.0	75.08	122.06
1.2	3.0	0.24	6.0	89.98	146.10

^aAs determined by a spectrophotometric technique following the disappearance of oxidant.

10^2 [MA] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³; 10^3 [TriPAFC] = 1.2 mol dm⁻³; 10 [H⁺] = 2.4 mol dm⁻³; 10^3 [Cat] = 6.0 mol dm⁻³.

Solvent composition : 50% acetic acid-50% water (v/v).

^bEstimated from pseudo-first order plots over 80% reaction.

increase in [TriPAFC]. The constancy of k_{obs} values at different [TriPAFC] reveals that the reaction follows a first order kinetics with respect to [TriPAFC]. Further it reveals that TriPAFC does not get diminished at our experimental conditions.

Under these experimental conditions, $[\text{MA}] \gg [\text{TriPAFC}]$, the concentration of MA is varied in the range of 1.0×10^{-2} to 3.0×10^{-2} mol dm⁻¹ at 303 K in the presence of 6.0×10^{-3} mol dm⁻¹ picolinic acid or 1,10-phenanthroline and keeping all other reactant concentrations as constant and the rates were measured (Table 3). The rate of oxidation increased progressively on increasing the concentration of mandelic acid. From the plot of k_{obs} versus [MA] it was established that the reaction shows first order dependence on [MA]. This result, coupled with the nearly unit slope value of the double logarithmic plot between k_{obs} and [MA] confirms the first order nature of the reaction with respect to [MA] (Fig. 1).

Effect of solvent polarity on reaction rate : The oxidation of mandelic acid has been studied in the binary mixture of acetic acid and water as the solvent medium. The reaction rate increased remarkably with the increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the solvent medium. These results are presented in Table 4.

Fig. 1. Showing order plot for the oxidation of mandelic acid in the absence and presence of PA and Phen by TriPAFC.

Table 4. Effect of varying solvent polarity on the rate of reaction in the presence and absence of picolinic acid and 1,10-phenanthroline at 303 K

%AcOH- H ₂ O (v/v)	Dielectric constant	1/D	10 ⁵ k ₁ (s ⁻¹)		
			No promoter	PA	Phen
30-70	72.0	0.0138	31.58	46.02	77.22
40-60	63.3	0.0158	36.60	52.64	85.66
50-50	56.0	0.0178	41.18	60.08	97.90
60-40	45.5	0.0219	56.68	72.66	118.60
70-30	38.5	0.0259	67.18	92.02	144.20

10² [MA] = 2.0 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [TriPAFC] = 1.2 mol dm⁻³; 10 [H⁺] = 2.4 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [PA] = 6.0 mol dm⁻³; 10³ [Phen] = 6.0 mol dm⁻³.

The effect from solvent composition on the reaction rate was studied by varying the concentration of acetic acid from 30% to 70%. The pseudo-first order rate constants were estimated for the oxidation of mandelic acid, with TriPAFC in the presence of perchloric acid at a constant ionic strength. The reaction rate increases markedly with the increase in the proportion of acetic acid in the medium (Table 4). When the acid content increases in the medium, the acidity of the medium is increased whereas the dielectric constant of the medium is decreased. These two effects cause the rate of the oxidation to increase markedly. The enhancement of the reaction rate with an increase in the amount of acetic acid generally may be attributed to two factors, viz. (i) the increase in acidity occurring at constant [H⁺], and (ii) the decrease in the dielectric constant with an increase in the acetic acid content.

The plot of $\log k_1$ versus $1/D$ (dielectric constant) is linear with positive slope suggesting the presence of either dipole-dipole or ion-dipole type of interaction between the oxidant and the substrate³⁵ (Fig. 2). Plot of $\log k_1$ versus $(D - 1)/(2D + 1)$ is a curvature indicating the absence of dipole-dipole interaction in the rate determining step. Positive slope of $\log k_1$ versus $1/D$ plot indicates that the reaction involves a cation-dipole type of interaction in the rate determining step.

Amis (1967) holds the view that in an ion-dipole reac-

Fig. 2. Plot of $1/D$ against $\log k_{\text{obs}}$ showing effect of solvent polarity for the oxidation of mandelic acid in the absence and presence of PA and Phen by TriPAFC.

tion involving a positive ionic reactant, the rate would decrease with increasing dielectric constant of the medium and if the reactant were to be a negatively charged

ion, the rate would increase with the increasing dielectric constant. In this case there is a possibility of a positive ionic reactant, as the rate decreases with the increasing dielectric constant of the medium³⁶. Due to the polar nature of the solvent, transition state is stabilized, i.e. the polar solvent molecules surround the transition state and result in less disproportion.

Thermodynamic parameters : The kinetics of oxidation of mandelic acid was studied at four different temperatures viz. 298, 303, 308 and 313 K at various percentage of acetic acid-water medium. The kinetics of oxidation of mandelic acid was also studied in the presence of picolinic acid and 1,10-phenanthroline. The second order rate constants were calculated (Table 5). The Arrhenius plot of $\log k_2$ versus $1/T$ is found to be linear. The enthalpy of activation, entropy of activation and free energy of activation were calculated from k_2 at 298, 303,

Table 5. Second order rate constants and activation parameters for the oxidation of *dl*-mandelic acid by TriPAFC at various percentage of acetic acid-water medium in the presence and absence of picolinic acid and 1,10-phenanthroline

%AcOH- H ₂ O (v/v)	$10^3 k_2$ (dm ³ mol ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)				E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	$-\Delta S^\ddagger$ (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹) (at 303 K)
	298 K	303 K	308 K	313 K				
No catalyst								
30-70	12.33	15.79	21.60	29.44	42.37	138.22 ± 5.1	42.89 ± 1.7	84.77 ± 3.2
40-60	14.29	18.30	25.47	34.69	46.34	133.44 ± 2.7	43.81 ± 0.9	84.24 ± 1.7
50-50	16.08	20.59	28.62	39.44	46.91	131.13 ± 2.7	44.23 ± 0.9	83.96 ± 1.7
60-40	20.02	28.34	34.83	48.11	44.04	138.41 ± 3.5	41.35 ± 1.2	83.29 ± 2.3
70-30	25.21	33.59	42.49	59.63	43.27	137.82 ± 3.2	40.40 ± 1.1	82.16 ± 2.1
Picolinic acid								
30-70	17.98	23.01	29.97	41.28	42.69	143.96 ± 1.5	40.01 ± 0.5	83.62 ± 1.0
40-60	21.11	26.32	34.29	46.44	40.71	149.14 ± 5.4	38.10 ± 1.8	83.28 ± 3.5
50-50	23.83	30.04	38.03	49.80	37.91	157.56 ± 3.9	35.42 ± 1.3	83.16 ± 2.6
60-40	28.99	36.33	49.48	60.33	37.87	155.83 ± 3.9	35.23 ± 1.3	82.45 ± 2.6
70-30	36.95	46.01	55.04	75.70	36.00	160.24 ± 3.0	33.50 ± 1.0	82.05 ± 1.9
1,10-Phenanthroline								
30-70	27.30	38.61	45.34	61.83	40.40	147.80 ± 3.0	37.91 ± 1.1	82.69 ± 2.0
40-60	32.33	42.83	49.87	68.56	37.28	156.87 ± 3.0	34.66 ± 1.0	82.19 ± 1.9
50-50	36.69	48.95	57.65	74.65	34.65	161.39 ± 5.4	33.12 ± 1.8	82.02 ± 3.5
60-40	44.80	59.30	73.20	92.07	35.98	155.64 ± 3.5	34.27 ± 1.2	81.43 ± 2.3
70-30	56.10	72.10	92.70	116.70	37.96	150.09 ± 1.5	35.42 ± 0.5	80.89 ± 0.9

$10^2 [\text{MA}] = 2.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $10^3 [\text{TriPAFC}] = 1.2 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $10 [\text{H}^+] = 2.4 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $10^3 [\text{PA}] = 6.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$; $10^3 [\text{Phen}] = 6.0 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$.

308 and 313 K using the Eyring relationship by the method of least square and presented in Table 5. The entropy of activation is negative for mandelic acid in the absence and presence of picolinic acid and 1,10-phenanthroline.

Mechanism of oxidation :

Reaction mechanism for TriPAFC oxidation of dl-mandelic acid in the absence of a promoter : From the product analysis, DNP was confirmed. Hence, it shows that under the experimental conditions employed in the present study, mandelic acid is oxidized to phenyl glyoxalic acid. Based on the above kinetic observations the following mechanism is proposed for the reaction. Absence of any effect of added acrylonitrile on the reaction discounts the possibility of a one-electron oxidation, leading to the formation of free radicals. The presence of a substantial kinetic isotope effect in the oxidation of DMA confirms the cleavage of the α -C-H bond in the rate-determining step. Therefore, a hydride-ion transfer in the rate determining step is suggested. Positive slope of $\log k_1$ versus

$1/D$ plot indicates that the reaction involves a cation-dipole type of interaction in the rate determining step. The negative entropy of activation in conjunction with other experimental data supports the mechanism outlined in Scheme 1.

Reaction mechanism for TriPAFC oxidation of dl-mandelic acid in the presence of a promoter : The findings with promoter can be explained by considering the reaction mechanism outlined in Scheme 2 and Scheme 3. Picolinic acid (Scheme 2), and 1,10-phenanthroline (Scheme 3) readily form complexes (C_1) with Cr^{VI} which are active oxidants³⁷⁻⁴⁰. In the next step, the complex reacts with the substrate to form a ternary complex (C_2). This ternary complex (C_2) undergoes redox decomposition by two electron transfer within the cyclic transition state in a rate determining step involving simultaneous rupture of C-C and C-H bonds to give a phenyl glyoxalic acid and the Cr^{IV} -promoter complexes.

Scheme 1. Mechanism of oxidation of mandelic acid by TriPAFC.

Scheme 2. Mechanism of oxidation of mandelic acid by TriPAFC in the presence of picolinic acid.

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Scheme 3. Mechanism of oxidation of mandelic acid by TriPAFC in the presence of 1,10-phenanthroline.

Conclusions

The kinetics of oxidation of mandelic acid has been investigated in aqueous acetic acid medium by spectrophotometrically at 303 K in the absence and presence of promoters like picolinic acid and 1,10-phenanthroline. The oxidation of mandelic acid by TriPAFC is first order each with respect to the mandelic acid, TriPAFC and hydrogen ion. The oxidation is catalysed by perchloric acid. The lowering of dielectric constant of reaction medium increases the reaction rate significantly. The reaction does not show the polymerization, which indicates the absence of free radical intermediate in the oxidation. The reaction becomes faster with each of the promoters.

References

- S. S. Mansoor and B. H. Asghar, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2013, **90**, 1395.
- B. Ozgün, A. Yaylaoglu and K. Sendil, *Monatsh. Chem.*, 2007, **138**, 161.
- F. Gharib, K. Zare, S. Ghammami and R. Ebrahimi, *Russ. Chem. Bull.*, 2005, **54**, 462.
- S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *Reac. Kinet. Mech. Catal.*, 2010, **100**, 21.
- S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **89**, 69.
- S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 2011, **225**, 249.
- S. S. Mansoor and S. S. Shafi, *Arab. J. Chem.*, 2014, **7**, 171.
- S. Ghammami and S. Dastpeyman, *J. Chin. Chem. Soc.*, 2008, **55**, 229.
- S. Ghammami and A. Hashemzadeh, *Bull. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2004, **25**, 1277.
- S. S. Mansoor, V. S. Malik, K. Aswin, K. Logaiya and A. M. Hussain, *J. Saudi Chem. Soc.*, 2013, doi: org/10.1016/j.jscs.2012.09.013.
- B. Saha, M. Islam and A. K. Das, *Prog. React. Kinet. Mech.*, 2005, **30**, 145.
- Z. Khan, S. Masan, Raju and Kabir-ud-Din, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2003, **28**, 881.
- S. Meenakshisundaram and R. Markkandan, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2004, **29**, 308.
- S. Meenakshisundaram and N. Sarathi, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2006, **31**, 569.
- M. Islam, B. Saha and A. K. Das, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2006, **38**, 531.
- A. K. Das, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2004, **248**, 81.
- M. Islam, B. Saha and A. K. Das, *J. Mol. Catal. (A)*, 2007, **266**, 21.
- R. Saha, S. K. Ghosh, A. Ghosh, I. Saha, K. Mukherjee, A. Basu and B. Saha, *Res. Chem. Intermed.*, 2013, **39**, 631.
- S. K. Ghosh, A. Basu, R. Saha, A. Ghosh, K. Mukherjee and B. Saha, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2012, **65**, 1158.
- J. Mandal, K. M. Chowdhury, K. K. Paul and B. Saha, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2010, **63**, 99.
- K. M. Chowdhury, J. Mandal and B. Saha, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2009, **62**, 1871.
- R. Saha, A. Ghosh and B. Saha, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 2011, **64**, 3729.
- R. Bayen, M. Islam, B. Saha and A. K. Das, *Carbohydr. Res.*, 2005, **340**, 2163.
- P. Swami, D. Yajurvedi, P. Mishra and P. K. Sharma, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2010, **42**, 50.
- S. Z. Ahmed, S. S. Shafi and S. S. Mansoor, *Asian J. Chem.*, 2013, **25**, 921.
- V. Kumbhat, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2000, **34**, 248.
- K. K. S. Gupta, B. Pal and P. K. Sen, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1999, **31**, 873.
- A. Kothari, S. Kothari and K. K. Banerji, *Indian J. Chem.*, 2000, **39A**, 734.
- N. Nalwaya, Jain and B. L. Hiran, *Oxid. Commun.*, 2003, **26**, 561.
- N. Vyas, A. Daiya, A. Choudhary, M. Sharma and V. Sharma, *Eur. Chem. Bull.*, 2013, **2**, 859.
- D. Garg and S. Kothari, *J. Chem. Sci.*, 2004, **26**, 333.
- N. Malani, M. Baghmar, P. Swami and P. K. Sharma, *Prog. React. Kinet. Mech.*, 2008, **33**, 392.
- V. Sharma, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1997, **74**, 607.
- V. Sharma, P. K. Sharma and K. K. Banerji, *J. Chem. Research (S)*, 1996, 290.
- G. J. Scatchard, *Chem. Phys.*, 1939, **7**, 657.
- E. S. Amis, "Solvent Effects on Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic Press, New York, 1967, 42.
- M. Islam, B. Saha and A. K. Das, *J. Mol. Catal. (A)*, 2005, **236**, 260.
- A. K. Das, A. Roy and B. Saha, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2001, **26**, 630.
- S. K. Ghosh, A. Basu, R. Saha, R. Nandi and B. Saha, *Curr. Inorg. Chem.*, 2011, **1**, 204.
- S. K. Ghosh, R. Saha, K. Mukherjee, A. Ghosh, S. S. Bhattacharyya and B. Saha, *J. Korean Chem. Soc.*, 2012, **56**, 164.